

Towards Inclusive Employment in Africa the case of Tanzania: Fast-Tracking Aspiration Six in Agenda 2063

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Abstract:- Agenda 2063 (the Africa we want) is a common strategy for Africa's inclusive growth and sustainable development for the coming fifty years which was endorsed by the African leaders in 2013 when they marked the 50th anniversary of African Unity (OAU). The objective of Agenda 2063 is to achieve seven Aspirations with the associated goals meant to move Africa closer to achieving the vision 2063. These seven Aspirations show African's desire towards shared prosperity and well-being, for togetherness and integration, for a continent of free people and broadened horizons, attainment of full potential for women and youth, and for fearless freedom and disease. This paper is based on Aspiration number 6 which calls for African inclusive development including social inclusion, inclusive education and employment.

Despite myriads of policies on disabilities in Africa, inclusive employment in Tanzania adequately achieved. What are the major issues of concern? Is it the Policy to blame here? or the problems with implementation issues? Which appropriate actions should be taken? These are the concerns are raised in this paper using the qualitative approach and the interpretivist paradigm. The study identified the extent of inadequate policy implementation tools hinder disability inclusion in employment and proposed intensification of available tools by *Tool-fortification* which imply intensifying efforts on available tools as means for policy implementation and fast-tracking the realization of Aspiration 6 of Agenda 2063 (the Africa we want).

Keywords:- Agenda 2063, Aspiration 6, Inclusive Employment, Disability Employment, Tool-Fortification.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Author is a human resources practitioner at a public institution in Tanzania with experience of more than fifteen years. Among other, duties of human resources officers include recruiting employees and the associated administration issues. Less than 5 people with special needs were employed, this does not mean that there aren't any disabled people in society. According to Tanzania President's Office Public Service Management (2007), it is estimated that there are 354,000 with special needs and only 2% are employed in

public institutions and calls for more effort is required to address this situation.

Historically, in Tanzania and the whole of Africa, considerations in various services and opportunities for people with special needs have been and continue to be very limited if not neglected. These and many other factors limit people with special needs from enjoying equal rights in employment opportunities, despite governments' laudable initiatives including developing policies that specifically address the issues of equality and inclusion of those with special needs. For instance, in Tanzania, the Disable Person Employment Act No. 2 (1982) established a quota system with the mandate for employers to employ 2% of a company's workforce to be people with special needs. All the National Advisory Council that provides guidance to the minister in charge of matters related to people with special needs was created. Despite all of these efforts, the employment of people with special needs is like an incurable disease.

The main goal of this work is to establish suitable approach and procedures to alleviate and facilitate the inclusion of people with special needs in work places. This needs to include the strengthening the systems for implementation of existing policies to comply with Aspiration 6 of Agenda 2063 the Africa we want. This must go hand in hand with the Disability Inclusion in employment for Africa. Numerous studies on disability-inclusive employment have been conducted highlighting the various reasons that cause inclusiveness to fail and are attributed to the employer and policies. For the employer, they include depriving attitude towards people with special needs and limited access to employment opportunities as well as non-supporting policies with unclear instructions on how to maintain an inclusive workplace (Steffens, L. (2021), ESCAP, U. and WHO, (2015), Asch. A, and Fine. M, (1988). Without considering whether the current policies are effective as expected, therefore, the primary goal of this paper is to examine strategies for implementing inclusive disability employment in Africa and realizing Aspiration 6 in Agenda 2063 of Africa we want. The Agenda 2063 is Africa's development blueprint to achieve inclusive and sustainable socio-economic development over 50 years (AU, 2013).

II. METHODOLOGY

Studies can either be qualitative which involves figures or qualitative which does not involve figures. Straus and Curbin, (1998) stated that qualitative means the type of research that produces findings without the use of statistical procedures or other means of quantification. In this regard, the observation and interpretation paradigm is used as stated in Claude, H. (2016), “it provides an opportunity for the voice, concerns, and practices of research assistant to be heard and the interpretive paradigm allows researchers to be co-creators of knowledge, Henning et al, (2004). This current study employed a qualitative method. As a result, the author’s views have been used to enable the study to be thorough while comparing the literature. It is far to note that, the 15-year field experience gained by the author substantially provides insights into real-world experiences while limiting some subjectivism. Therefore, the aim of this study is to identify factors that need fast-tracking for the successful implementation of Aspiration 6 of Agenda 2063 as provided under African Unity in the year 2013.

III. ASPIRATION 6 IN A GLANCE

The Agenda 2063 has 7 aspirations and each aspiration has its own goal which if achieved will move Africa close to achieving its vision. For instance, Aspiration 6 states that “Africa whose development is people driven, relying on the potential of African people, especially its women and youth and caring for children” (African Unity). It has been insisted that ‘all citizens of Africa will be actively involved in all aspects of decision making. Africa shall be an inclusive continent where no child, woman or man will be left behind or excluded on basis of gender, political affiliation, religion, ethnic affiliation, locality, age or other factors’. This Aspiration has two specific goals: The first goal is full gender equality in all spheres of life by eliminating all forms of discrimination in political, economic, and social. The second goal is on engaged and empowered youth and children by creating opportunities for Africa’s youth, access to health, education, and jobs (African Union, 2013).

This aspiration and its goals can be realized if intentional efforts are taken to ensure that what is written is put into practice, as stated by the African Union. According to Claudine (2016), in order for Aspiration 6 to be realized, Africans need to live in a continent without gender bias in all spheres of life, including the workplace. Aspiration 6 talks about gender equality, “no child, woman or man will be left behind or excluded, on the basis of gender, political affiliation, religion, ethnic affiliation, locality, age or other factors” that means Aspiration 6 is promoting inclusion of all person in Africa regardless of a disability. Therefore, next section highlights how Aspiration 6 defines the rights of the disabled, (specifically on employment engagement), and the relationships between Article 19 section 2 subsection a-g of Protocol to the African Charter on Human and people’s rights

on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in Africa, (Banjul Charter, 2018).

IV. NEXUS BETWEEN ASPIRATION 6 AND PROTOCOL TO THE AFRICAN CHARTER ON HUMAN AND PEOPLE’S RIGHTS ON THE RIGHTS OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES IN AFRICA

Agenda 2063 it is a continuation of the Pan- African drive over centuries, for unity, self-determination, freedom progress and collective prosperity persuaded under Pan-Africanism and the African renaissance, (African Unity, 2013). It is built on, and seeks to accelerate the implementation of past and existing continental initiatives for growth and sustainable development, relying upon the above lights it is safe to state that Aspiration 6 seeks to implement the protocol of the African Charter on Human and people’s rights on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in Africa; because the protocol addressed, among other things, the inclusion of people with disabilities in employment. Article 19 section 2 (a-g) specifies the rights of people with disabilities in relation to employment and work. It has prohibited all kinds of discrimination to people with disability on all matters in employment, it has pinpointed the inclusive employment, sub section ‘d’ specific directed public sectors to employ people with disability together with reserving and enforcing minimum job quotas for employees with disability.

Thus, Article 19, when read in conjunction with Aspiration 6, is quite clear that they all oppose stigma against the disabled and emphasize that disabled people have the same right to be employed as abled people.

Africa of 2063 will be free from all forms of gender parities, with disability inclusion in all forms of employment and disabilities will fully integrated in public service as well. During a five-day training on disability mainstreaming and implementation of the continental plan of action on the African decade of persons with disability held in Dakar, Senegal 23 May 2018 the Policy and decision makers were urged to promote disability inclusion and acknowledge that disability is an evolving concept; they were exhorted to add this action plan on the state's agenda. Many African nations have up to this point already created plans and policies for safeguarding the rights of people with disabilities, for instance, there are several policies addressing the rights of people with disabilities in Tanzania, as was previously mentioned that Tanzania has rectified the United Nation Convention on the Rights of Person with Disability (CRDP) as well as passed the 2010 Persons with Disability act and implemented National Policy on Disability of 2004.

V. DISABILITY AND EMPLOYMENT IN AFRICA

Understanding the causes and contributing factors that led to the underrepresentation of people with disabilities in the workforce is essential. Everybody's life is impacted by employment since it offers a path to social inclusion and a means of obtaining the essential financial resources for one's well-being, work can have a significant impact on how we categorize, relate to, and interact with one another, Mourad, (2009) and Goffman (1959). However, studies demonstrate that due to a number of barriers to inclusivity, inclusive employment has not been achieved in the world. People with impairments are routinely overlooked as potential employees. "In every workplace, perception, fear, myth, and prejudice continue to hinder understanding and acceptance of disability", (United Nations, 2021). Heather (2011) mentioned that disabled people perceive that employers are discriminating them, Jackie et al (2022) research revealed that people with disabilities face numerous barriers to securing jobs which include established negative assumptions on the ability of disabled people; Employers frequently view disability inclusion as challenging, a danger to revenues, or a purely altruistic endeavor satisfying their company's CSR. There are several myths, such as that people with disabilities cannot work and that it is expensive to accommodate them in the workplace moreover employers sometimes perceive that employing people with disability can be a burden to them because they assume that disabled might need constant support and much time for adaptation of work as well as the environment, and even when employed, people with disabilities still encounter a number of difficulties at work, such as unfriendly workplaces, unfair treatment when it comes to promotions and career advancement (Marescia, 2003).

In developed nations, the unemployment rate for people with impairments of working age is between 50% and 70%, compared to 80% to 90% in developing nations. (United Nations 2021). Some studies have indicated that, the exclusion of people with impairments from the labor market has a significant macroeconomic cost, For instance, the International Labour Organization estimates that the annual cost of excluding people with disabilities can be as high as 7% of a nation's GDP. Based on these factors, people with disability are facing challenges in attaining their dream from societies to employment, as a result, the significant poverty rate among them also put them at on lower status in societies. Against this background, it is vital that immense efforts be made to address the matter and this study suggests for tools for implementing policies on inclusive employment be revisited and improved. It is proposed that, African nations adopt what is refer to as *Tool-fortification* (that means intensifying efforts on available tools). The following chapter will look at a way to achieve *Tool-fortification*.

VI. TOOL-FORTIFICATION APPROACHES

In spite of having good policies on disability, the employment levels of persons with disabilities have not been significantly impacted by policies, their representation in the paid sector remains low globally and their situation is not yet improved (Edwards et al. 2010). People with disability in Africa and specifically in Tanzania are still lagging behind employment, that means the inclusion have not been successful attained. This situation provide evidence that regales of the availability of policies and Acts, there is no guarantee on inclusiveness of employment. What is needed are instruments that adequately promote the adherence on policies in order to achieve the desired goals. Consequently, it is necessary to strengthen the current instruments. African government should therefore revisit available instruments to see if they are still relevant to enable the successful implementation of available policies and is crucial (Mohamad, 2013). These instruments are also known as "governing tools" therefore "the implementation of governing tools is usually made to achieve policy targets." Ally (2013) reviewed Howlett's (2005) work on policy evaluation. Howlett's proposed four instruments for effective policy implementation: Nodality/informational, Authority/coercive, Treasury/ financial, and Organization/institutional (NATO). In line with the proposition, this study adopts the "Authority/coercive" and leave other factors because it is perceived that "authority" is the most crucial factor because it is difficult to achieve great results without effective government involvement, and resources and information may be accessible, but nothing will happen if the government decides not to actively participate in implementing. Okoroma, (2006) worked on Education Policy and Problem for Implementation in Nigeria and pinpointed that lack political-will affect the implementation of education policy because leaders' actions were not patriotic but for personal motive, as a result, they forget about implementing policies.

Authority; is the "legitimate power that a person or group is granted to practice over others" (Shonna, 2021). According to Brinkerhoff, (2010) authority is the "commitment of actors to undertake actions to achieve a set of objectives" in this case, implementation of inclusive employment the authority also can be defined as authorities as processes or individuals which organize the cooperation in a community by an assigned social position that allows to create and maintain environments and thereby influence the behavior of individuals" (Andringa, et al., 2013). There is a relationship between exercising power with political will thus why commonly, the term "political will" is used to describe the seat of authority. (Abazović and Mujkić, 2015). Therefore, from the light above, there is relationship between policy implementation and political will thus is why political will (authority) is crucial in policy implementation.

According to Brinkerhoff (2010), the focus on speeches and other public announcements by high-ranking individuals (government officials), adoption of domestic legislation, and/or ratification of international agreements or treaties is where the hunt for political will indicators begins. Absent an opportunity of some sort of tangible action, such declarations alone are insufficient indicators of political intent. A lack of political will is frequently viewed as being indicated by inaction. In the case of inclusive employment, when government fails to enforce sanctions and or pursue insubordination cases against employers who are not implementing this policy have termed as a lack of political will. For example, failure to pass legislation, enforce sanctions, or pursue corruption cases in the courts have all been employed in the absence of a political will.

Therefore, this study is recommending the government to use its authority to implement inclusive disability employment by imposing penalties and introducing special auditing.

Imposing penalties and fines on all employers who do not comply with the policy, particular, Article 31 which mandates employers to recruit and retain employees with disabilities and establishes a workforce quota that requires any employer with a workforce of 20 or more employees to employ persons with disabilities at a rate of at least 3% of the overall workforce. According to OECD (2006), the most cost-effective punishment in criminal and civil actions for enforcing compliance is likely the imposition of a monetary fine, the amount of which is calculated by reference to the nature of the violation and the circumstances. Becker, S. (1968) in his writings on economic regulations, has identified the monetary penalty as a policy instrument that enforces a person or organization to comply with the policy or regulation. Therefore, if employers will be imposed with penalties or/and sanctions definitely they will implement the policy.

Involvement of stakeholders; by involving stakeholders means, the government is supposed to mobilize all stakeholders, in this regard employers, people with disabilities, social activists, and media to promote the implementation of inclusive employment by joining hands with civil societies which advocate disability issues, for instance in Tanzania there is Federation of Disabled People and the Tanzania Gender Networking Programme by encouraging public education initiatives, and engagement with civic organizations, and the private sector until the matter is known by all for easy implementation.

Also, the government should introduce special auditing (compliance auditing), the goal of compliance auditing is to maintain high-quality control mechanisms to guarantee accountability, transparency, and adherence to public administration policies and regulations (Slobodanyk, Y., et al. 2018). Compliance auditing will oversee how employers are complying with the available policies. Based on my experience most of the time governments concentrate much on

auditing fiscal issues and forget other crucial aspects like gender balance at work, organizations' compliance level with policies and government directives, and if they do carry out such an audit, non-financial factors are not given the same weight as financial factors. Ernest. (2018), argued that is important to give equal weights to all aspects (financial and non-financial) during auditing as each element matters for the well-being of the organization and government. Employers will become aware of rules and government requirements, and inclusive employment will be implemented as a result of compliance auditing.

VII. CONCLUSION

The full commitment and involvement of African member states are necessary for the achievement of Aspiration 6 on Agenda 2063, "Africa We Want.". Leaders of African states. The African Union's goals should be successfully achieved, and African country leaders should make conscious efforts to assure this, by intensifying available policies and monitoring the implementation of those policies, particularly in regards to issues of inclusive employment, because, despite the Disability Policy's existence, it is currently only being implemented in theory. Therefore, African nations must work with academics, activists, and community groups to promote inclusive employment, Cooperative efforts between nations are crucial for spreading effective strategies and best practices.

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